

THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN TRANSFORMING THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article presents the theoretical views of scientists regarding the correct evaluation of the possibilities of effective digital marketing in the process of transforming the financial management system in the activities of business entities and its use.

Key words: financial management, digital marketing, marketing opportunities, marketing technologies, performance evaluation, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, small business and private entrepreneurship.

Introduction.

Modernization of production in business activities in Uzbekistan, technical and technological renewal, formation of a competitive environment for economic sectors, mastering the production of fundamentally new types of products and technologies, ensuring the competitiveness of national goods in domestic and foreign markets, as well as entrepreneurship consistent measures are being taken to improve the management of the activities of its subjects based on digital technologies. In this regard, the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said, "In order to achieve development, it is necessary and necessary to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. It gives us the opportunity to take the shortest way to rise" [1] and it is not for nothing that they say.

Within the framework of the national program "Digital Uzbekistan-2030", the implementation of priority projects on the digital transformation of the

financial and banking system is considered as the main task. [2]

In turn, it is expected that by 2025 there will be about 30 smart cities in the world, 5% of them will be located in North America and Europe, which is also a proof of the perspective of digital marketing. Digital marketing is becoming big business, with data from 2022 showing that marketing budgets will account for an average of 11.2 percent of company revenue. In the US, this equates to more than \$196 billion in annual industry spending. In Great Britain it is 24.2 billion US dollars [3].

As a proof of these arguments, it is possible to see that in the West alone, the companies that are forming in accordance with digital opportunities and promoting them more widely are becoming effective business representatives (for example: Apple, Microsoft, Facebook, Alphabet, AT&T, Amazon, Verizon Communications, such as Google) [4].

Analysis of literature on the topic.

Theoretical approaches to evaluating the effectiveness of digital marketing in the transformation of the financial management system are reflected in the scientific research of a number of domestic and foreign scientists. In particular, Russian researchers M.V. Zakharova, M.A. Kurasova, T.V. Deynekin, V.M. Komarov, S.A. Mikhalev and S.G. Pesikov looks at evaluating the effectiveness of digital marketing from the perspective of digital marketing communications.

Research methodology.

Methods and approaches such as theoretical and practical study, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis were used in the preparation of the article.

Analysis and results.

Considering the fact that not all aspects of the issue have been fully explained in the theoretical and practical developments on the evaluation of the effectiveness of digital marketing in the transformation of the financial

management system in our country, we consider it appropriate to reflect on this issue, referring to the research works of foreign scientists.

T.V. Considering the effectiveness of Internet advertising, it is noted that most of the methods of evaluation of effectiveness are based on the analysis of information about visits to websites created by technical means (external counters and analytical systems, log files and advertising placement systems). emphasizes. The difference in the communication aspect of digital marketing is to evaluate the user activity on the website in terms of the actions they perform: landing pages, registrations, applications, orders, sales, etc.[5] Thus, T.V. Deinekin considers a comprehensive approach to evaluating the effectiveness of advertising activities on the Internet, highlights four main stages of the communication process between an advertiser and Internet users in Internet marketing (Table 1).

T.V. Dynekin provides the maximum possible number of pointers. Currently, every free analytical system (Yandex.Metrika», Google Analytics, etc.) is provided and captures many other data. However, based on the specifics of this research, small businesses monitor a number of key indicators, such as the number of visitors and cost, actions on landing pages (sites), targeted inquiries (applications), orders, sales, etc. goes

Table 1

A system of performance indicators at the stages of the communication process between advertisers and Internet users

Stage	Performance indicators	
	Communicative	Economical
Display advertising	Number of impressions, number of unique impressions, audience	Cost to place an ad, cost per thousand impressions,

message	overlap, frequency of impressions	cost per thousand unique impressions
Interest	Impression rates, recall rates, recognition rates, clicks, unique clicks, responses (impressions per click)	Cost per click, unique click cost
Visit the website	Number of unique users, number of visits, frequency of visits, number of new users, geographical distribution of users, number of page views, depth of views, website paths, duration of visits	Cost per unique user, cost per visit
Movement	Number of moves	Number of orders, number of customers, number of sales, sales volume, average purchase amount, average number of sales per customer, cost per action, order value, sales price, customer value, order frequency

According to the study, digital marketing technologies are seen as "changing the processes of interaction with the target audience" and small organizations only convert a high part of this interaction into results (bids, orders and sales). they analyze from the point of view. Small businesses use the indicator "targeted requests (applications) of potential customers" as a way to establish communication between digital marketing and traditional marketing

activities. We believe that small businesses need mechanisms that allow them to coordinate and target groups or clusters of indicators that influence the quality of the target audience and the ability to convert to a real buyer.

It should be noted that reducing the effectiveness of digital marketing to the cost of actions in the form of clicking on advertising materials does not always guarantee addressing the target audience, that is, a user may click on a link, but it may not be relevant to the target market of the advertised product.

Ideas for evaluating the effectiveness of an advertising company on the Internet M.V. It was developed in the work of Zakharova, in which pricing models for evaluating an advertising company are considered. Based on the analysis of price models, the author found that the advertising company has a two-stage feature: they use various methods of digital marketing (banners, text blocks, advertising in search engines, catalogs, etc.) is a company website whose performance is measured using pricing models.

Development of ideas for evaluating the flow of information resulting from the use of digital marketing methods M.A. Kurasova and it was reflected in the works of S.G.Pesikov, M.A. Kurasova points to the continuity of digital marketing effectiveness assessment and emphasizes the need to fix user paths in an analytical system, and believes that each user path should be tracked from the moment they enter the site to the moment they exit [6]. At the same time, the considered indicators do not show in detail the process of conversion of information flow from Internet marketing communications to the actions of visitors on landing pages, which only reflect the overall effectiveness of advertising in Internet marketing.

Transition to evaluation of online advertising effectiveness in the context of enterprise efficiency It was reflected in S.G.Pesikov's work. The author considers the effectiveness of Internet advertising as a multifactorial concept that includes social, economic, and legal effects, and emphasizes that the estimate of

the cost of contacting the user is limited. In communications, factors such as attention, preference, and the continuity of the user's access to the resource are important.

S.G. The approach to evaluating the effectiveness of Internet advertising presented by Pesikov reflects the interaction of economic and communicative effectiveness indicators, which is fair, because each communicative effect in Internet marketing has a reasonable economic generalization. But considering only basic and relevant needs seems a bit artificial.

In our opinion, the flow of information in Internet marketing should be changed based on Internet marketing communications directed to specific landing pages when necessary to meet the needs of the user (or opt out of the flow by refusing to respond to ads and visit the site).

Focusing on the following considerations, we consider it appropriate to dwell on the relationship between the concepts of "Internet traffic" and "information flow" in marketing. Information flow means an orderly movement of information characterized by its direction, intensity, density and usefulness [7].

Thus, we can conclude that Internet traffic in marketing is a type of information flow that includes units of the target audience of the enterprise. However, taking into account the lack of clear theoretical approaches to the concept of "traffic" and the limitations of the relationship of this concept with other types of business flows, the marketing concept of Internet traffic in this article refers to the process of interaction with the target audience on the Internet of the concept of "Internet marketing information flow". considered as a synonym that can be defined as the movement of information about the results of conversion, in terms of the validity of considering the characteristics of the information flow of digital marketing, the author relies on relevant studies of marketing flows [8].

1) The transition to considering the flow of information is related to the main important feature of digital marketing technologies. They are considered from the point of view of three types of processes (communication, conversion and monetization processes) that are changed by changing the properties generated from information flows. The basis for the formation of the information flow of digital marketing is created in various forms of changing internet marketing communications affecting the online and offline environment (omnichannel marketing features) [9]. Digital marketing communications are converted into applications (requests) for the goods, works and services of enterprises, which, in turn, become commercial and financial flows of enterprises.

2) Information flow characteristics of Internet marketing are presented in advertising systems, search results, social output and other communication channels of Internet marketing. The characteristics of the landing pages of Internet sites are determined by the information field in which the flow of information is directed (the quality of the sales offer of the organization presented in text and multimedia content, types of feedback, completeness of the description and other characteristics of the landing pages).

3) In this study, taking into account the indicator of "targeted requests (applications) of potential customers and the formed classification of Internet marketing technologies, the conversion of communications into targeted requests (applications) of potential customers and subsequent sales is influenced by digital marketing processes. and can be described in terms of the changes in information flows that shape digital marketing technologies. In this case, there is an interaction of two different information flows of digital marketing:

4) Information-communication flow (IKP) of digital marketing, which includes communication data about digital marketing activities (number of clicks, number of impressions, coverage);

5) Information and financial flow of digital marketing (IFP), including

financial information on digital marketing activities (cost of targeted action, cost of program, cost of order, cost of sale). Turning to information flows in terms of determining the specific features of the formation of information-communication and information-financial flows of digital marketing M.I. It allows to complete the functional features of external and internal conversion provided by injection.

If, according to M.I. Ukolov's approach, external conversion is considered as a share of the site's audience, a standard marketing effect that can convert it to customers, then external conversion not only changes the site's audience, but also the communication processes that occur in advertising systems includes.

Consequently, the information and communication flow of digital marketing is formed in the change of the information provided in the internet site audience and internet marketing communication advertising systems. Then the main task of external conversion is to convert the flow of information and communication into communications with the target audience (clicking on ads), which then lead to targeted actions (pages, registration, messages through feedback forms, etc.) becomes

The main interest is what happens after the flow of information and communication is transformed into targeted actions. In digital marketing, targeted action (CPA) distinguishes visitors who have shown interest but are not interested in a company's products. Then there are two possible actions for the visitor:

- 1) the visitor leaves the landing page of the website after determining that the product does not meet his needs (or for other reasons). Such a visitor temporarily leaves the commercial relationship (can be returned with special advertising campaigns using redirection methods) or permanently becomes a non-target audience unit for this organization;

- 2) expresses the desire to continue cooperation with the visiting company and move to the next stage of trade relations. This behavior of the visitor is

described as the conversion of the target action into a target request (application). A visitor to the landing page of the site sends a targeted request (application) for the company's goods, works and services.

In addition, according to M.I. Ukolov, in the process of internal conversion, targeted inquiries (applications) of potential customers are converted into buyers (and not individual website visitors). The process of converting a potential customer's inquiry into a purchase is not based on the characteristics of the organization presented on the website (the site did its job by converting the contact into an application), but on the conversion process of the organization from the targeted inquiries (applications) of potential customers to information and real customers.) and money flow expressed by the quantity and quality of sales (Internet marketing monetization technologies), that is, begins to depend on the ability to interact with financial flow. As we noted at the beginning of the study, monetization is considered along with communication and conversion as a separate process of Internet marketing that forms digital marketing technologies.

Therefore, the information and financial flow of digital marketing is formed as a result of changes in the website audience in the form of target requests (applications) of potential customers and information provided in the process of evaluating the economic efficiency of Internet marketing (monetization).

The review of the processes of changing information flows that make up digital marketing technologies is aimed at the change of the form of information flow as a result of the influence of external and internal conversion on the landing pages of Internet sites. This leads not only to the consideration of communicative and economic efficiency (T.V. Deynekin, A.Y. Muzika, V.M. Komarov, etc.), but also to the determination of the effectiveness of the website's landing page - conversion efficiency.

When considering the change in digital marketing information flows under

the influence of the conversion process, E.P. Mikhaleva and S.A. The works of Fedotov are noteworthy [10]. The authors consider conversion in Internet marketing in relation to the levels at which the target audience - visitors to the web pages - are located, and calculate the performance indicators that occur when the potential target audience interacts with the organization's website. determine.

A step-by-step approach to considering the conversion of Internet sites allows you to identify the main stages of information flow changes. All of these include website pages, target audience source site pages, online advertising campaigns, and advertiser website pages.

Thus, many researchers consider different types of metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of digital marketing. The main problem is that modern digital marketing allows us to analyze more than a hundred different indicators and indicators. Based on the theoretical study of the specific characteristics of digital marketing activity indicators of small business enterprises, it was found that the main characteristic of evaluating the behavior of site visitors depends on the duration of actions. So, if a visitor is not only interested in advertising and enters the site, but also contacts company managers, asks for a price list, asks questions and leaves communication information, joins a group on a social network and performs other actions 'ng, we can conclude that it is active. Even if the visitor has not sent an application describing his purchase intention, his activity indicators allow to make decisions about the prospects of such a visitor to lead to a purchase and the prospects of a selected segment of the target audience for a small business.

In the dissertation, the work of researchers who considered the indicators of digital marketing effectiveness in terms of activities and actions performed by the user on the organization's website was analyzed. Thus, T.V. Deinekin [11], L.M. Kapustina and I.D. Mosunov [12], A.Y. Muzika, as well as foreign digital

marketing practitioners J.R. Saura, P. P. Sanchez, and L. M. Cerda-Suarez [13] consider the following performance measures. (See Table 2)

Table 2

Activity and actions performed by the user on the Internet site are a measure of efficiency

№	Measurements	Description
1	Number of shows	total number of advertising communications. Each time an advertisement is displayed, an advertising communication is established. The data source is determined by each standardized internet marketing advertising system (Yandex.Direct, Google.Adwords, Facebook.Ads, Target.Mail, etc.);
2	Number of visitors (pass through advertisement or click)	unique users who visited the organization's website as a result of the advertising effect (advertising contacts in the form of impressions);
3	CTR (click-touch-rate)	click-through rate, the ratio of the number of clicks on ads to the total number of impressions. In our opinion, this is the first indicator of information flow conversion, because it reflects the transition of user attention to interest by clicking on the ad;
4	Target actions on the page	the number of targeted actions on the page (application in feedback forms, contacting an online consultant, sending one's contact information, etc.);
5	On-page targeted inquiries	readiness, message about the intention of the target audience units to make a transaction (purchase of

	(applications) (leads)	goods, work or services);
6	sale (sale)	purchase of goods, works and services of enterprises by the target audience (website visitors);
7	Conversion	the ratio of the number of goals achieved to the total number of visitors.

As you know, conversion is divided into external and internal. External conversion determines the change in the flow of information and communication in advertising systems of digital marketing communications. Internal conversion determines the change of information and financial flows on the organization's website in the form of information provided in the processes of targeted inquiries (applications) of potential customers and evaluation of economic efficiency (monetization) of digital marketing.

The process of converting digital marketing indicators based on the activity and actions of users on the Internet D.A. Livshin and L.I. given by Voronova [14]. Researchers focus on conversion as a factor in the success of an advertising company, considering this concept as the percentage of users who pass certain stages on the way to purchase.

Thus, the information flow of interaction with the target audience is changed on the landing pages of the organization's website, which makes it possible to include conversion efficiency in the groups of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of Internet marketing technologies. The group of indicators that combine the communicative, economic, and conversion efficiency of landing pages of Internet sites and are the most suitable for the specific characteristics of small business activities are the indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of Internet marketing based on the activity and behavior of visitors to the Internet site. This allows to create a system of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness

of digital marketing technologies in small enterprises.

Each digital marketing technology includes indicators of communicative efficiency, conversion efficiency of website landing pages, and economic efficiency.

The flow of information and communication is primarily determined by the indicators of communicative efficiency, as it includes information about the impressions, clicks and actions of the target audience on the landing pages of the websites of the organizations that are converted during external conversion processes.

Thus, the basis for the systematization of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of digital marketing technologies in small business is the behavioral approach to the evaluation of effectiveness, taking into account the actions of visitors - target audience units - on the landing pages of the organization's website. A system of indicators was formed and mathematically described to evaluate the effectiveness of digital marketing technologies in terms of changing the flow of information. Information and communication flow (ICP) and information and financial flow (IFP) are highlighted. Each of the digital marketing technologies includes communicative, conversion and economic efficiency indicators. A type of conversion efficiency is proposed, which describes the conversion of communicative efficiency indicators into economic efficiency indicators of digital marketing technologies.

Conclusions and suggestions

1. As part of the study of the technological nature of digital marketing, the author adopted methods and decisions in the field of changing the processes of interaction of the target audience with digital marketing communication channels aimed at obtaining specific market results, taking into account the existing limitations in the activities of small enterprises. defined in the concept of digital

marketing technologies as a set of tools. Also, a classification was made based on the study of digital marketing processes, including communication, conversion and monetization technologies of Internet marketing.

2. A system of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of digital marketing technologies in terms of changing information flows was formed. The information-communication and information-financial flows of digital marketing were determined within the research, and their interaction allows to evaluate the communicative, conversion and economic efficiency of digital marketing technologies.

3. A methodical approach to the development of digital marketing technologies, the process of transferring the company's target audience from less targeted to more targeted quantitative and behavioral characteristics of costs was formed, which allows to take into account the unique forms and indicators of digital marketing. It allows to describe the process of interaction between classic and digital marketing in terms of complementing the flow of information with classic marketing performance evaluation indicators that can be digital in digital marketing analytical systems and accepted by small businesses. will give.

4. The scientific-theoretical foundations of marketing in the digital environment have been formed in accordance with the stages of ICT development, and modern digital marketing technologies have a high potential to influence consumers by introducing elements used in direct and indirect traditional marketing activities. To date, the main reason why the management of economic entities does not accept all the possibilities of the digital environment is that they perceive the costs of implementing digital technologies to be high. Also, it is extremely necessary to recognize digital transformation in the business environment as an optimal direction in solving several tasks aimed at increasing marketing efficiency.

1. List of used literature:

2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Raqamli_Iqtisodiyot
3. 3. Decree No. PD-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 on the approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation // Information on national legislation base, 06.10.2020, No. 06/20/6079/1349.
4. <https://megatrands.ru>
5. Top 100 Digital Companies I/ Forbes (publishing house) <https://www.forbes.com/top-digital>: companies/list/#tab:rank (murojaat sanasi: 01.12.2021y.)
6. Дейнекин Т. В. Оценка эффективности предпринимательской деятельности в сфере интернет-рекламы: автореф. дис. ... канд. экон. наук: 08.00.05. – М., 2003. – С. 19–23.
7. Курасова М. А. Совершенствование маркетинговой деятельности предприятий на основе внедрения интернет-технологий: автореф. дис. ... канд. экон. наук: 08.00.05. – М., 2005. – С. 19.
8. Рязанцев В. Д. Большая политехническая энциклопедия. – М.: Мир и Образование, 2011. – С. 355.
9. De Cleen, P. Flow marketing: Content, Conversatie, Conversie: Go with the flow. – Amsterdam: Lannoo Campus, 2018. – 200 p.
10. Самойлов И. В. Знание-центрическая методика перехода предприятий к деятельности на основе интернет-маркетинга // Креативная экономика. – 2011. – № 1. – С. 117–123.
11. Михалева Е. П., Федотов С. А. Оценка эффективности мероприятий интернет-маркетинга // Известия Тульского государственного университета. Серия: Экономические и юридические науки. – 2015. – № 3-1. – С. 92.

12. Дейнекин Т. В. Оценка эффективности предпринимательской деятельности в сфере интернет-рекламы: автореф. дис. ... канд. экон. наук: 08.00.05. – М., 2003. – 32 с.

13. Капустина Л. М., Мосунов И. Д. Интернет-маркетинг. Теория и практика продвижения бренда в сети: монография. – Екатеринбург: Изд-во Урал. гос. экон. ун-та, 2015. – 102 с.

14. Saura J. R., Palos-Sanchez P., Cerda-Cuarez L. M. Understanding the Digital Marketing Environment with KPIs and Web Analytics // Future Internet. – 2017. – Vol. 9, no. 76. – P. 1–13.

15. Лившин Д. А., Воронова Л. И. Математическое моделирование в маркетинге при построении рекламных кампаний // Современные наукоемкие технологии. – 2014. – № 5. – С. 209.